

ARENA Research Unit

Abstract Representations in Neural Architectures

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE
FOR SOFTWARE SYSTEMS

FIAS Frankfurt Institute
for Advanced Studies

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ARENA Research Unit

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Preamble

ARENA is a DFG funded Research Unit (FOR 5368), which was established in June 2023 at Goethe University Frankfurt. Professor Christian Fiebach is the speaker and Professor Gemma Roig is the co-speaker of this unit. ARENA consists of 7 interdisciplinary research projects that aim to better understand how knowledge is organised at different levels of abstraction - both in the brain and in AI models, and both in the form of concrete visual objects and in their linguistic representation. This research unit is a collaboration between Goethe University, the Max Planck Institute for Software Systems, and the Frankfurt Institute for Advanced Studies.

The aim of this document is to provide an overview of the activities and progress of the ARENA Research Unit during the first 6 months of its establishment, from June to December 2023. We will briefly review all the guidelines and plans developed by the Coordination Team, such as the Knowledge Transfer and Outreach Plan, the Data Management Plan and the Communication and Engagement Plan. There will also be an overview of the progress and deliverables of the project. We will briefly present the efforts made by ARENA for its early career researchers to provide them with the necessary networking opportunities, organisation of workshops and further development of soft skills.

I. Project kick-off

The ARENA Research Unit initiated its work in July 2023 with its kick-off meeting where all the partners gathered and got acquainted. The projects, tasks and expectations were discussed and the path for the collaborations ahead was explored. The projects, tasks and expectations were discussed and the way forward for the collaboration was explored. The coordination office officially started its work and shared its action plan. Project communication tools and media such as mailing lists, website, Zenodo community¹, Discord messaging platform and shared working environment on Hessianbox were established.

II. Project Meetings

The ARENA project investigators meet every month to discuss their progress, status, potential obstacles and collaborations. Each meeting lasts 2 hours. In 2023 there were 5 meetings. All meeting minutes and recordings are archived for further reference in the ARENA shared internal repository.

III. Deliverables

The 7 projects of the ARENA Research Unit have a total of 76 deliverables to be delivered over a period of 4 years. In the first 6 months, 5 deliverables have been completed. All deliverables of the projects are available on the Zenodo ARENA Community.

- Stimuli set, image dataset, pilot - P1_Melissa [M4]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10007605>
- Data Management Plan - P0_Coordination [M5]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10053874>
- Knowledge Exchange and Transfer Plan - P0_Coordination [M5]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398981>
- ARENA multimodal dataset - P6_Roig [M5]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10060785>
- Communication and Engagement Plan - P0_Coordination [M6]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10219905>

IV. Outreach and knowledge transfer activities

Following the plans and guidelines of the ARENA Knowledge Exchange and Transfer Plan, a number of activities and opportunities were planned and provided in the first period (months M1 to M6).

Following the request of the ARENA Early Career Researchers, 2 workshops have been organised for the coming months, a workshop on the EEG/MEG analysis toolbox MNE-Python (speaker: Dr. Jack Taylor, FiebachLab) and the Net2Brain toolbox developed in the lab of Gemma Roig (speakers: Dr Bhavin Choksi and Timothy Schaumlöffel, Computational Vision and Artificial Intelligence group). In addition, 2 prominent external speakers have been invited for 2024, Professor Tommy Poggio, Mercator Fellow of the ARENA unit, and Professor Martin Hebart. Moreover, in the 6-month period there has been 4 publications by the ARENA members which the full list can be accessed on the ARENA website².

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/arena>

² <https://neuroai-arena.github.io/publications>

Outreach activities also include the updating of the ARENA website and establishment and systematic use of an ARENA channel on X (Twitter); see next section.

V. Communication activities

According to the ARENA Communication and Engagement Plan, several means and methods are planned for the dissemination of ARENA results and findings, as well as for external and internal communication.

The ARENA X (Twitter) handler (@ARENA_ResUnit) has been activated and is aiming at having a strong online presence. The ARENA website (<https://neuroai-arena.github.io>) is where all information about the Unit, its projects and the team is gathered and regularly updated. In order to keep the team informed about the status of the projects, the latest related news as well as upcoming deadlines and tasks, there are bi-weekly update emails sent out by the coordination office.

The Early Career Researchers (ECR) meet twice a month. In the context of the monthly ECR meeting, the ARENA researchers have the opportunity to discuss the progress of their projects and any obstacles they might face. Another monthly meeting is the Journal Club, where the discussions go beyond their projects and they bring new ideas, introduce interesting scientific papers, etc. In the period of 6 months, the ARENA ECRs had 4 meetings in each category.